

Alkali Metal Complexes : Homobinuclear Complexes of Alkali Metals with *bis*-(8-Hydroxy-5-Quinoly)-Methane

DHARM PRAKASH*

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800 005

and

SHANKAR PRASAD SINGH

Department of Chemistry, A. N. College, Patna-800 013

Manuscript received 10 March 1981, revised 31 August 1981, accepted 30 October 1981

Complexes of alkali metals, belonging to $M_2L_2H_2L$ type, where $M=Li, Na, K, Rb$ or Cs and $H_2L=bis$ -(8-hydroxy-5-quinoly)methane have been obtained. While the ligand and its salts are white and green respectively, the complexes are light brown in colour. Their ir spectra indicate the presence of hydrogen bonding in them, which may be one of the dominant factors for their stability. Coordination is suggested by negative shifts in addition to splittings of 3335 and 1580 cm^{-1} bands of the ligand, assigned to stretching $-OH$ and stretching $-CN$ vibrations respectively. Negative shifts of bending $-OH$ vibration mode occurring at 1420 cm^{-1} in the ligand provide further support to the existence of coordination in these compounds.

IN an attempt to explore the mechanism of selective absorption of alkali metal ions by plants, with the assumption of course that a knowledge of coordination chemistry of alkali metals would facilitate fuller understanding of the mechanism, our attention has been drawn to the ligand *bis*-(8-hydroxy-5-quinoly)methane (Fig. 1), henceforth designated as H_2L .

Experimental

Preparation of the ligand: The ligand *bis*-(8-hydroxy-5-quinoly)methane was prepared by the method of Horowitz and Perros^a. Its authenticity was established by elemental analyses, melting point determination and ir spectrum. The m.p. was found to be 280° against the reported value^a of 283° .

Fig. 1

This ligand behaves as a quadridentate ligand and has been shown to form stable complexes¹⁻⁵ with a number of transition metals. It, however, appears from literature survey that no alkali metal complex with *bis*-(8-hydroxy-5-quinoly)methane has yet been reported. It was, therefore, decided to examine this ligand for possible complex formation with alkali metals.

We could obtain a number of homobinuclear alkali metal complexes with this ligand. They have the general formula $M_2L_2H_2L$ where $M=Li, Na, K, Rb$ or Cs and $H_2L=bis$ -(8-hydroxy-5-quinoly)methane. Complexes were synthesised by at first preparing a di-alkali metal salt of the ligand and then refluxing it with the ligand itself in requisite proportions in DMF.

Preparation of alkali metal salts of H_2L : A mixture of H_2L and an alkali metal hydroxide in the mole ratio 1 : 2 was refluxed in DMF at 120° for about 3 hr, the solution being constantly stirred with the help of a magnetic stirrer. The separated green salt was filtered, washed with solvent ether and dried in an electric oven. Salts, having the general molecular formula M_2L [where $M=Li, Na, K, Rb$ or Cs and $L=$ deprotonated *bis*-(8-hydroxy-5-quinoly)methane], were obtained.

Preparation of neutral complexes: A mixture of H_2L and its di-alkali metal salt M_2L (in the mole ratio 2 : 1) was refluxed in DMF at 120° for 4-6 hr with constant stirring. The dark brown solution so obtained deposited light brown solid on cooling. This was filtered, washed first with DMF and finally

TABLE 1

Compound	Colour	m.p./decomposition temp. (°C)	Found%				Calcd. %			
			C	H	N	M	C	H	N	M
H ₂ L	White	280 m	75.8	4.80	9.25	—	75.5	4.64	9.26	—
Li ₂ L	Light green	>320 d	72.80	3.90	9.24	—	72.61	3.82	8.92	—
Li ₂ L.2H ₂ L	Light brown	>320 d	74.74	4.80	9.25	—	74.51	4.36	9.15	—
Na ₂ L	Green	310 d	66.04	3.86	8.00	13.00	65.89	3.47	8.09	13.29
Na ₂ L.2H ₂ L	Light brown	195 d	72.80	4.50	8.85	4.85	72.00	4.21	8.84	4.84
K ₂ L	Deep green	>320 d	60.38	3.30	7.54	20.50	60.32	3.17	7.41	20.68
K ₂ L.2H ₂ L	Light brown	>320 d	70.00	4.55	8.56	8.00	69.65	4.07	8.55	7.94
Rb ₂ L	Green	>300 d	54.69	3.09	6.75	28.00	54.68	2.88	6.71	28.06
Rb ₂ L.2H ₂ L	Light brown	295 d	67.39	3.98	8.25	11.24	66.99	3.92	8.23	11.46
Cs ₂ L	Green	>300 d	40.59	2.50	4.80	45.54	40.28	2.12	4.95	46.99
Cs ₂ L.2H ₂ L	Light brown	290 d	58.70	3.59	7.18	22.72	58.46	3.42	7.18	22.73

TABLE 2

Compound	Selected absorption bands (in cm ⁻¹)				
	ν_{OH}		2800-1800	ν_{CN}	δ_{OH}
H ₂ L	3335ms	—	—	1580s	1420s
Li ₂ L	—	—	—	1595m, 1575m	—
Li ₂ L.2H ₂ L	3320br	3078vw	2300-2100br	1615s, 1582w	1408w
Na ₂ L	—	—	—	1570w	—
Na ₂ L.2H ₂ L	3125s	3322s	1900-1800br	1595m, 1575m	1400sh
K ₂ L	—	—	—	1610s, 1575s	—
K ₂ L.2H ₂ L	3240br	3060wb	2200-2000br	1595m, 1575m	1410w
Rb ₂ L	—	—	—	1610w, 1575w	—
Rb ₂ L.2H ₂ L	3325s	3060wb	1970-1850br	1592m, 1578m	1408w
Cs ₂ L	—	—	—	1595w, 1585m	—
Cs ₂ L.2H ₂ L	3320s	3065w	1950-1850br	1595m, 1576m	1408w

ms=moderately strong, m=medium, s=strong, w=weak, vw=very weak, sh=shoulder, br=broad and wb=weak broad.

with solvent ether and then dried in an electric oven at 100°.

Results and Discussion

Some physical properties as well as the analytical results of the ligand, its salts and the complexes are listed in Table 1.

H₂L is a white amorphous powder. It is insoluble in cold water, but yellowish colour in water is observed on heating. This indicates its partial solubility in water. On the other hand its salts, M₂L, are green in colour and are insoluble in water. On boiling with water, these salts decompose to give H₂L.

Unlike the ligand and the salts, the neutral complexes M₂L.2H₂L are brown in colour. They are only partially soluble in polar solvents such as DMF, DMSO, methanol, ethanol, pyridine and acetone, but are insoluble in non-polar solvents, namely, chloroform, diethylether, *n*-hexane, benzene and toluene.

Their high decomposition temperatures are suggestive of their polymeric nature. They are stable under dry conditions and are found to show no change in stoichiometry or physical properties even after one year.

Infrared spectra: Infrared measurements for the ligand, its salts and the complexes were made

between 4000-650 cm⁻¹ in Nujol mulls/Hexachlorobutadiene. Pertinent ir data are listed in Table 2.

The absorption bands of principal interest in the infrared spectrum of H₂L are 3335, 1580 and 1420 cm⁻¹. The moderately strong band at 3335 cm⁻¹ in its spectrum is attributed to the stretching -OH vibration frequency⁸. This band has disappeared in the spectra of the salts, whereas in the spectra of the complexes, this shows negative shifts in addition to splitting. In almost all the complexes, this band appears as split bands at ~3320 and ~3060 cm⁻¹. The most probable explanation of the splitting of the 3335 cm⁻¹ band of the ligand seems to be the simultaneous presence of (i) the coordinated and (ii) the free -OH groups in these complexes. The strong band at 1420 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of the ligand is, in all probability, due to the bending -OH frequency⁸. In the spectra of the complexes, they appear at 1408-1400 cm⁻¹, indicating a negative shift of 12-20 cm⁻¹. These features suggest that the coordination of the ligand with the alkali metals has taken place through the oxygen atom of the -OH group.

The absorption band at 1580 cm⁻¹ has been assigned to the stretching vibration of -C=N- group in the quinoline ring⁸. In the spectra of the complexes this band has split into two, one in the range 1615-1595 cm⁻¹ and the other in the range 1585-1575 cm⁻¹. It has been observed that while

the lower frequency of split band at $1585\text{-}1575\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is insensitive to the alkali metal, the other one, which is found at 1615 cm^{-1} in the lithium complex, appears at frequencies decreasing with the increase in atomic weight of the metal until for the caesium complex where it appears at 1582 cm^{-1} . This behaviour of the 1580 cm^{-1} band, observed in

double-faced bidentate ligand and that this ligand is coordinated to the alkali metal cations through nitrogen as well as oxygen atoms. Their ir spectra point also to the hydrogen bonding in them. These suggest a gross structure of the type shown below.

It is not claimed that the alkali metal ions are uniformly four-coordinate. The coordination

the ir spectrum of the ligand, is closely similar to that observed in the spectra of similar complexes of alkali metals with the simple oxine⁶ and also to that observed in the spectrum of the Ag-complex, bis(8-hydroxy-quinoline)silver(I)⁷, which has been shown to contain silver tetrahedrally surrounded by two oxygen and two nitrogen atoms and also to contain a strong hydrogen bond⁸. These features suggest the coordination of the nitrogen atom of the $-\text{C}=\text{N}-$ group of the quinoline ring with the central metal atom.

In addition to the above, a new broad band of weak to medium intensity in the region $2300\text{-}1850\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is observed in all the complexes. This band is absent in the spectra of either the metal salt or the ligand H_2L and could be assigned to $\text{O}-\text{H}\cdots\text{O}/\text{N}\cdots\text{H}-\text{O}$ absorption. Obviously, hydrogen bonding seems to be an essential feature of these complexes and this may be one of the factors stabilising them.

Probable structure : The above discussion indicates that in all these complexes, H_2L behaves as a

number could easily increase to six or more via intermolecular interaction.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. A. K. Banerjee and Dr. S. K. Roy, Readers, Department of Chemistry, Patna University for valuable suggestions. One of them (S. P. S.) is grateful to the U. G. C., New Delhi for financial assistance.

References

1. V. V. KORSHAK, S. V. VINOGRADOVA and T. M. BABCHINISTER, *Polymer Science, USSR*, 1960, **2**, 344.
2. V. V. KORSHAK, S. V. VINOGRADOVA and T. M. BABCHINISTER, *Vysokomolek Soedin*, 1960, **2**, 492.
3. E. HOROWITZ and T. P. FERROS, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 189.
4. D. N. SEN and P. UMAPATHY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 209.
5. R. C. POLLER and D. L. B. TOLEY, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 2373.
6. A. K. BANERJEE, A. J. LAYTON, R. S. NYHOLM and M. R. TRUTER, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, 2536.
7. B. P. BLOCK, J. C. BAILAR, Jr. and D. W. PEARCE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 4971.
8. J. E. FLEMING and H. LYNTON, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1968, **46**, 471.